

FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF MENDABLE Z-PINNED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the fracture properties and in-situ repair functionality of a mendable z-pinned carbon/epoxy composite laminate. The composite material is comprised of hybrid plies containing carbon fibre tows interlaced with mendable thermoplastic filaments of poly[ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid)] (EMAA) and reinforced in through-the-thickness direction by carbon fibre z-pins. The combined effect of thermoplastic interlacing and z-pinning on the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and self-healing efficiency of the composite are investigated. The results show significant increases in crack growth resistance, with increases to both the initiation and steady-state fracture toughness. The novel composite material exhibits unique functionality in relation to the repair of delamination cracks.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of light-weight laminated composite materials in structural engineering applications is wide-spread, largely due to their excellent in-plane properties, fatigue resistance and resistance to environmental degradation. Composite laminates are susceptible to delamination and matrix damage that typically stems from impact, fatigue loading or environmental degradation. An effective method for improving the delamination resistance of fibre-polymer composites is through-the-thickness reinforcement. The through-thickness reinforcement can be achieved using high stiffness, high strength fibres inserted by stitching, tufting, z-pinning or weaving [1-3]. Examples of engineering applications where z-pins have been used include the air inlet ducts and engine bay doors of the F/A-18E/F Superhornet [4], and the composite roll-over bars on Formula 1 racing cars [5].

Z-pinning has been shown to improve delamination and fatigue resistance of composite laminates subjected to mode I, mode II and mixed mode I/II loads [6-9]. Experimental and numerical fracture analysis has shown that the pin volume and diameter have a strong influence on the delamination resistance, with the delamination resistance increasing with either increasing pin volume content [3, 10] or decreasing pin diameter when the volume fraction is held constant [11]. The failure modes, hence effectiveness of pins, are also affected by pin length and inclination relative to the Z-direction [6].

However, a long-standing issue with through-thickness reinforced composites is the high-cost repair of damage which is typically caused by impact, over-loading, fatigue loading or environmental degradation. The damaged material must usually be repaired by patching over the damaged region (although the crack remains) or by scarf repair (replacing the defective material) [12]; with both repair methods being labour intensive and slow. A novel approach is to repair the damage *in-situ* within the three-dimensional (3D) fibre composite by modifying the fabric and/or the polymer matrix phase. To date, composite self-repair technologies have utilised microcapsules filled with self-healing agents [13-18], microvascular fibres to transport and release self-healing agents [17, 19-23], and mendable polymers [21, 24-27]. When damage occurs, the healing process can be self-activated or activated using external stimuli (e.g. heat) to repair the 3D composite and restore the mechanical properties [28, 29].

Composites incorporating mendable polymers have shown potential to self-repair delamination and matrix damage. One such mendable polymer is the thermoplastic poly[ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid)] (EMAA). Russel et al. [30] used EMAA as an inter-layer to restore the mode I and mode II fracture toughness of a carbon-epoxy laminate. The repairing ability of EMAA was also investigated by Pingakarawat et al. [31] who found efficient restoration of the static and fatigue fracture toughness in carbon fibre-epoxy laminates. Yang et al. [32] and Pingakarawat et al. [33] developed a novel composite containing self-healing EMAA filaments stitched in the through-thickness direction. The EMAA stitching was shown to increase the mode I delamination crack growth resistance while also providing self-repair capabilities. Another method developed by Ladani et al. [34]; involved a novel hybrid composite comprised of EMAA filaments and carbon fibre tows stitched through-the-thickness. The carbon fibre tows provided improved resistance to interlaminar delamination, while the EMAA filaments enabled self-healing capabilities. The method showed good repair of the delamination damage and partial restoration of the fracture toughness.

The effectiveness of EMAA for self-healing or in-situ repair of z-pinned composites has not been investigated. This paper presents an experimental investigation into the effectiveness of interlacing thermoplastic filaments along the X-Y plane of a braided carbon fibre reinforcement to promote in-situ self-repair functionality for z-pinned composites. A novel z-pinned polymer composite incorporating self-repair filaments was developed. The composite makes use of high-stiffness, high-strength carbon fibre z-pins to improve the through-thickness fracture toughness, while the ply-interlaced EMAA filaments provide self-repair capabilities.

2 COMPOSITE MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite materials and manufacturing

The composite fabric plies consisted of carbon fibre tows (DowAska), poly[ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid)] (EMAA) filaments (DuPont Packaging and Industrial Polymer), carbon fibre-bismaleimide (BMI) z-pins (Albany Engineered Composites Pty Ltd) and epoxy resin (Sicomin). The carbon fibre tows were 800 tex (12K). The epoxy resin was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DEGBA) resin (SR8100) hardened using a diamine-based hardener (SD8824). The EMAA pellets (NUCREL[®] 960 resin) were drawn into filaments using a 3devo filament maker operating at 135°C (zone 1), 155°C (zone 2), 145°C (zone 3) and 135°C (zone 4) and a screw speed of 2.5 rpm. The filaments had a circular cross-section diameter of 1.10 ± 0.02 mm. The EMAA contained ethylene acid copolymer with 19% by weight of methacrylic acid randomly distributed along the EMAA polymer chain. Using a Herzog radial braider, an EMAA-interlaced carbon fibre fabric was produced (figure 1). Braiding was conducted over a 50 mm diameter mandrel using a linear speed of 30 m/hr and horn gear speed of ~38 rpm. The resulting fabric weaving construction is ‘two over, two under’, ($\pm 45^\circ$ carbon fibre tows) alternating over and under the axial EMAA filaments.

Figure 1: Schematic of the dry EMAA-interlaced carbon fibre fabric.

Laminates were manufactured with and without z-pins. For the un-pinned laminate, the hybrid braided plies were stacked into preforms having a lay-up configuration of $[0/90]_{2s}$. The preform, consisting of eight plies, was infused with epoxy resin at room temperature using the vacuum bag resin infusion (VBRI) process. The resin and hardener were mixed at a ratio of 100:22 wt/wt and degassed prior to infusion. The laminate was cured under ambient conditions for 24 hours followed by post-curing in an oven at 60°C for 8 hours. For the z-pinned laminate, the hybrid fabric was stacked in the same way as the un-pinned laminate. After stacking, carbon fibre z-pins were inserted in the through-thickness direction into the preforms with the excess pin length projecting into a balsawood sheet on the underside. The z-pins were evenly spaced in a grid pattern such that the pin volume fraction was 1%. After pinning, the preform was infused in the same way as the un-pinned laminate.

2.2 X-ray computed tomography analysis

The microstructure of the composite laminates was assessed before the delamination experiment, and after self-healing via X-ray computed tomography (CT) using a General Electric Phoenix v|tome|xS instrument fitted with a micro-tube. Scans were performed at 60 kV and 350 μ A with a voxel size of 25.8 μ m. Up to 2000 image projections were recorded per specimen which were merged to generate the 3D volume of the specimen and extract two-dimensional (2D) sectional images.

2.3 Double cantilever beam testing

The mode I fracture toughness of the laminates was evaluated using a 10 kN Instron testing machine. These experiments were conducted using the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens in accordance with ASTM D5528 standard. The DCB specimens were 150 mm long, 25 mm wide and had a 50 mm long pre-crack along the mid-plane to initiate delamination as shown in figure 2. The pre-crack was manufactured by inserting a 30 μ m-thick film of polymethylpentene (PMP) prior to infusion. The specimens were reinforced by two 12-ply unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy laminates (VTM-264, supplied by Advanced Composites) to prevent excessive bending and damage to the beams due to the high fracture toughness of z-pinned composites. The reinforcing laminates were bonded to the DCB specimens using an epoxy-paste adhesive, Araldite 420[®] (supplied by Huntsman). T-tabs were bonded to the DCB specimen using Araldite 420[®] for tensile loading of the DCB specimen.

Figure 2: Schematic of the DCB test specimen.

The fracture toughness was measured by monotonically increasing the crack opening displacement (COD) at a rate of 1 mm/min. The crack length was measured using a travelling microscope alongside the DCB specimen with the modified beam theory used to calculate the mode I fracture toughness according to:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

where the applied load and load point displacement are denoted by P and δ , respectively. a , b and Δ are the delamination length, specimen width and effective delamination extension to correct for rotation, respectively. Four specimens were evaluated for each configuration.

2.4 Self-healing

Healing was conducted by exposing the laminates to 150°C for 30 min, which was determined to provide the optimum healing condition for EMAA [35]. The healed composites were cooled to room temperature prior to measuring the mode I fracture toughness.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Laminate geometric properties

The microstructure of the infused laminates was assessed using x-ray CT analysis. Figure 4 shows the infused laminates and their constituents. The volume fraction of the carbon fibre and EMAA were determined using ASTM D3171 and X-ray CT analysis, respectively. The volume fraction of the carbon fibres and EMAA filaments were found to be 0.25 and 0.14, respectively.

Figure 4: X-ray CT imagery of a) un-pinned and b) pinned composite.

The inclination of the z-pins in the pinned specimens was assessed using X-ray CT analysis. Figure 5 shows a frequency distribution of the z-pin inclination angle. The mean z-pin inclination angle was found to be 4.5° with standard deviation 16.4°. These values are in good agreement with the z-pin inclination measured in literature for similar systems [36, 37]. The variation in z-pin inclination was attributed to deflection from the EMAA filaments and carbon fibre tows as well as the manual handling of the pinned preforms.

Figure 5: Frequency distribution of z-pin inclination.

3.2 Fracture toughness properties

The mode I fracture toughness properties of the laminates with and without z-pins are shown in figure 6a and 6b. The R-curves shown in figure 6a for both the pinned and un-pinned laminates revealed increasing crack growth resistance with increasing delamination length until a quasi-steady-state fracture toughness was achieved. The increasing crack growth resistance of the un-pinned laminates was attributed to the interaction of EMAA filaments with the crack tip plastic zone. As seen in the X-ray CT and optical microscopy images in figure 7a, cylindrical EMAA filaments induced crack deflection, crack branching and crack arrest at discrete locations, which led to the increase in fracture toughness with delamination length for the un-pinned material. In comparison, the rising R-curve behaviour of the z-pinned laminate was due to the formation of a large-scale crack bridging zone by the z-pin, as seen in figure 7b. The bridging z-pins provided traction load that resisted the crack opening and reduced the applied stresses at the crack tip, thereby improving the fracture toughness. In addition, the extent of crack branching and bifurcation for the pinned laminate was substantially greater than the un-pinned laminate. This was due to the increase in load distribution along the through-thickness direction due to the presence of the reinforcing carbon fibre z-pins.

Figure 6: The effect of z-pinning on **a)** R-curves, and **b)** initiation and steady-state fracture toughness of the un-pinned and pinned composites, showing the percentage change in fracture toughness due to z-pinning.

The steady-state fracture toughness of the un-pinned and pinned laminates was 3.48 ± 0.08 and 8.52 ± 0.41 kJ/m², respectively. Z-pins increased the steady-state fracture toughness by 5.03 kJ/m²

(144%). However, there was no apparent improvement to the initiation fracture toughness for the pinned laminates. This is because, at 1% volume content, z-pins are spaced at ~ 2.5 mm which is greater than the sub-millimeter crack growth occurring at delamination crack initiation. At such small delamination length, z-pins are largely dormant, and the fracture toughness is therefore governed by the matrix toughness. It is well established that the presence of z-pins does not affect the initiation fracture toughness with similar initiation fracture toughness values for pinned laminates previously reported [6]. Nevertheless, z-pins become more effective at longer delamination lengths due to the crack bridging zone formation as discussed earlier. The standard deviation measured in the steady-state fracture toughness of the pinned laminate were greater than for the un-pinned laminate, and this was attributed to the variation in pin inclination angle which has been shown to influence pin failure modes and failure energy, both of which contribute to the interlaminar toughening [37].

Figure 7: X-ray CT imagery showing damage in a) un-pinned and b) pinned composites.

3.3 Healing of composites

Following DCB evaluation of the laminates, both the un-pinned and pinned delaminated specimens were healed and re-evaluated to quantify the recovery of the interlaminar fracture toughness. The load versus crack opening displacement data from the DCB tests for both composites before and after healing are given in figure 8. The un-pinned composite in the healed condition showed similar fracture loads compared to the pristine composite, thus suggesting a complete recovery of the fracture toughness properties after healing. In contrast, the pinned laminate showed a reduction in the fracture loads in the healed state compared to the pristine composite, indicating partial recovery of the fracture toughness from the healing process.

Figure 8: Load-displacement curves for the un-pinned and pinned composites before and after healing.

The initiation and steady-state fracture toughness values of the composites before and after healing are compared in figure 9a and 9b, respectively. The initiation fracture toughness values (figure 9a) of

the un-pinned and pinned laminates after healing were 0.46 ± 0.01 and 0.63 ± 0.16 kJ/m², respectively. The un-pinned and pinned composites showed similar reductions to the initiation fracture toughness, indicating incomplete healing or change to the EMAA-based toughening mechanism. The steady-state fracture toughness values of the un-pinned and pinned laminates after healing were 3.75 ± 0.49 and 4.15 ± 0.94 kJ/m², respectively. The steady-state fracture toughness of the un-pinned laminate fully recovered, indicating successful healing of the delamination crack. In comparison, only 50% recovery of the steady-state fracture toughness of the pinned laminate was achieved from the healing process.

a)

b)

Figure 9: The effect of healing on **a)** initiation, and **b)** steady-state fracture toughness for the un-pinned and pinned composites, showing the percentage change in fracture toughness after healing.

When thermally activated at 150°C, EMAA melted and flowed into the delamination crack. The flow of EMAA into the delamination crack was assisted by a pressure delivery mechanism, inherent to this thermoplastic. The ensuing acid-amine and acid-hydroxyl reactions (eqn.2 and eqn.3, respectively) produce water. At high temperature, the water phase-separated generating an internal pressure within the EMAA. The expanding gaseous water phase forced the molten EMAA into the delamination crack. Upon cooling to ambient temperature, the EMAA formed an adhesive-like layer bonded to the epoxy matrix, as shown in figure 10.

As shown in the X-ray CT images in figure 10, a substantial repair of the delamination crack in both the un-pinned and pinned laminates was achieved from the healing process, although a few areas of unhealed damage were evident. The flow of the EMAA is evident by the voids left behind at locations previously occupied by EMAA filaments. The voids were generated by pressurised gasses from the EMAA-epoxy reaction and were the driving force behind the flow of the molten EMAA.

Figure 10: X-ray CT imagery of the a) un-pinned and b) pinned composites following self-healing.

Although, the X-ray CT images show effective healing of the delamination crack in both the un-pinned and pinned laminates, high magnification optical microscopy images (see figure 11) showed incomplete repair of the z-pin/laminate interface. The reduction to the steady-state fracture toughness of this composite after healing observed in figure 9b (4.37 kJ/m^2) is similar to the increase in the steady-state fracture toughness from z-pinning (5.03 kJ/m^2). This is indicative of the loss of the z-pin toughening mechanism in the healed composite. To enable a complete repair of the z-pin/laminate interface, it is paramount that EMAA flows into the pull-out hole left behind by the z-pin. Upon unloading of the DCB specimen, the z-pins were observed (see figure 10) to reoccupy the pull-out hole, and create a tight interference fit with the laminate. This prevented the flow of EMAA into the z-pin/laminate interface during healing. Therefore, the repair of the z-pin/laminate interface was limited to the area of intersection between the delamination crack plane and the z-pin. Thus, a large portion of the z-pin/laminate interface remained unrepaired and this maybe the reason for the partial recovery to the mode I steady-state fracture toughness of the healed z-pinned laminate.

Figure 11: Optical microscopy imagery of a carbon z-pin **a)** in pristine and **b)** repaired laminates.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the effect of interlacing thermoplastic filament with carbon tow in a braided fabric on the repair of delamination. Compared to the un-pinned laminate, the pinned laminate exhibited significant improvements in crack growth resistance due to through-thickness toughening from the z-pins. However, while repair of the delamination crack was achieved in both materials, the z-pin/laminate interface was not effectively repaired. In the pinned laminate, inadequate flow of EMAA into the z-pin/laminate interface resulted in loss of the z-pin toughening mechanism in the healed laminate, resulting in incomplete recovery to the fracture toughness properties. Although the z-pin toughening mechanism was partially reinstated, the crack growth resistance of the self-repaired z-pinned laminate remained equal to that of the un-pinned laminate.

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